

On the Supposed Occurrence of Acids with Uneven Number of Carbon Atoms in Vegetable Oils and Fats. Part I. Daturic Acid from the Seeds of *Datura Stramonium*, Linn.

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The vast majority of fatty acids isolated from vegetable oils and fats are found to contain an even number of carbon atoms. However, in the literature, many instances have been reported of the occurrence of fatty acids with an odd number of carbon atoms. The existence of such acids has always been looked upon with considerable doubt and the occurrence of none of them has been questioned by later investigators.

The acid $C_{17}H_{34}O_2$, known as daturic and margaric acids, has been said to occur very widely in oils and fats. The earliest mention of this acid is by Gerard (*Compt. rend.*, 1880, 111, 305). He claims to have obtained it by the fractional precipitation of the solid acids from the oil of *Datura stramonium* seeds. Holde (*Chem. Zentr.*, 1902, II, 1417) confirmed the presence of this acid in the above source, but questioned its individuality a little later (Holde, Ubbelonds, and Marcusson, *Ber.*, 1905, 38, 1347). Meyer and Beer (*Monatsh.*, 1918, 33, 311), as a result of detailed investigations, claim to have definitely established the individuality of daturic acid, as well as its identity with margaric acid. In view of this work Elsdon ("Edible oils and fats", 1926, p. 30) has stated "This is the only acid with an uneven number of carbon atoms, that has been definitely proved to exist in an oil. It is one which is, therefore, of great theoretical interest and which may very well repay further study."

Reference must be made next to the work of Verkade and Coops (*Biochem. Z.*, 1929, 206, 468) on the methyl esters of the solid acids from the oil of *Datura stramonium*. They subjected these to fractional distillation in vacuum and from a comparative study of the

melting points of the various fractions with those of the synthetic mixtures of the methyl esters of palmitic and stearic acids, they concluded that daturic acid is really a mixture of palmitic and stearic acids.

The chief difficulty in investigations of this nature arises from the fact that fatty acids are apt to form eutectic compounds, behaving as regards melting and solidifying points, like pure chemical substances, which cannot be easily resolved into their components either by fractional precipitation or crystallisation (Lewkowitsch, "Chemical Technology and Analysis of Oils, Fats and Waxes," 6th Ed. Vol. I, pp. 118-21; Francis, Piper and Malkin, *Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1930, **A123**, 214). The ternary system, palmitic, synthetic margaric and stearic acids has recently been studied by Schriener, Fulton and Burks. (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1933, **55**, 1494). The curve for palmitic and stearic acids indicates the formation of a compound, very close to the equimolecular ratio at 57.5° . The freezing points of margaric acid with the equimolecular mixture have also been studied. The drop in the freezing point is not very great. Although this drop could be easily detected by accurate melting point determinations, it will pass unnoticed in the ordinary mixed melting point determinations. Since the melting points given in the literature for daturic acid vary from 54° to 60° , it can be easily seen how an approximately equimolecular mixture of palmitic and stearic acids may be mistaken for daturic acid and also why mixed melting points are not conclusive evidence for identification.

By intensive fractionation of the methyl esters, Francis, Piper and Malkin (*loc. cit.*) have been able to separate mixtures of solid acids into nearly chemically pure acids and when this method was applied to the separation of the solid acids of the oil of *Datura stramonium*, they were found to consist of palmitic and stearic acids together with small quantity of lignoceric acid. No trace of daturic acid could be obtained.

EXPERIMENTAL.

For purposes of this investigation, the seeds were specially grown and collected under careful supervision. The oil content was found to be 16.3%. About 6.2 kg. of the seeds were extracted with petroleum ether (b.p. 50° - 60°) in a large soxhlet. On distilling off the solvent 1020 g. of a pale yellow oil were obtained.

TABLE I.

Physical and chemical constants of the oil.

Sp. gr. at 25°	0.9184	Acetyl value	25.6
n at 25°	1.4735	Reichert-Miesel value	0.44
Saponification value	187.1	Total fatty acids	87.7
Iodine value (Hanus)	122.6	Percentage of unsaponifiable	
Acid value	5.6	matter	2.6

The oil (1 kg.) was saponified with sodium hydroxide. The resulting soap, after extraction with ether to obtain the unsaponifiable matter, was dissolved in water and acidified with hydrochloric acid when the insoluble fatty acids (855 g.) were liberated. These were separated into the saturated and unsaturated acids by Twitchell's method (*Ind. Eng. Chem.*, 1931, 13, 806).

TABLE II.

Chemical constants of the fatty acids.

Mean M. W. of mixed acids	289.1	Mean M. W. of solid acids	263.2
Iodine value of mixed acids	120.7	Mean M. W. of liquid acids	304.4
% of solid acids	13.1	Iodine value of liquid acids	126.5

The unsaturated acids.—The unsaturated acids were obtained as a yellowish brown oil. They were purified by the distillation of their methyl esters under diminished pressure.

10 G. of the acids were oxidised with cold dilute permanganate (Lewkowitsch, *loc. cit.*, Vol. I, p. 575). The mixture of insoluble hydroxy acids was filtered and dried. From the filtrate no hexahydroxy acid could be isolated. On extracting the dried precipitate with ether in a small soxhlet, dihydroxystearic acid (m.p. 136°, M. W. 316.1) was obtained. The residue left after extraction of the dihydroxy acid was treated with 5—6 litres of boiling water and the aqueous extract on cooling deposited crystals of tetrahydroxystearic acid (m.p. 172°-73°, M. W. 352).

Another 10 g. of the acids were treated with bromine according to the method of Eibner and Mugenthaler (Lewkowitsch, *loc. cit.*, Vol. I., p. 585). No other insoluble compound was obtained. From the ether soluble compounds, tetrabromostearic acid (m.p. 113-14°, M.W. 597.1) was obtained.

The above results establish the presence of oleic and linolic acids among the unsaturated acids.

Unsaponifiable portion.—The unsaponifiable matter was dissolved in 95% alcohol and treated with decolourising charcoal. After repeated crystallisations, a phytosterol (m.p. 134°) was obtained. Its acetate melted at 129°.

The saturated acids.—The saturated acids (110 g.) were almost colourless and their methyl esters (111 g.) were subjected to fractional distillation under reduced pressure. Each fraction was then carefully refractionated in high vacuum several times and the following fractions were finally obtained:

TABLE III.

Fraction.	Range of temperature.	Wt. of ester.	Mean M. W. of acids from saponification value.
1	up to 152°	2.75 g.	258.3
2	152°-55°	82.2	256.2
3	155°-57°	0.70	...
4	157°-60°	0.20	...
5	160°-65°	5.50	255.0
6	165°-70°	2.20	263.1
7	170°-72°	10.60	278.6
8	above 172°	1.80	283.9
	Total distillate	105.95	
9	Residue and loss	5.05	

Fractions 1 to 5, weighing 91.35 g. consisted of pure methyl palmitate and on saponification gave palmitic acid (m.p. 61°, M. W. 256).

From fraction 6, a small quantity of pure stearic acid (m.p. 68°, M. W. 284.3) was obtained. The mother liquors gave palmitic acid (m.p. 61°, M. W. 257). Fraction 7 yielded 6 g. of pure stearic acid (m.p. 70°, M. W. 258). The residues from the above were concentrated and some more stearic acid (m.p. 69°; M. W. 282.8) was isolated. Fraction 8 was found to be pure methyl stearate.

The residue 9 was coloured. The liberated acid was dissolved in alcohol and boiled with charcoal. After two crystallisations about 3 g. of an acid melting at 71° (M. W. 356.5) were obtained. The acid on repeated crystallisations melted at 76-77° and had a molecular weight of 371. Its *p*-phenylphenacyl ester was prepared according to the

method of Drake and Bronitsky (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1930, **52**, 3715). The ester melted at 101.2° and its melting point was not altered by mixing it with a pure sample of the *p*-phenylphenacyl ester of lignoceric acid.

SUMMARY.

As a result of the detailed chemical examination of the oil from the seeds of *Datura stramonium*, the following constituents were identified:

Unsaturated acids—Oleic and linolic acids.

Saturated acids—Palmitic and stearic acids together with a small quantity of lignoceric acid. No daturic acid could be detected.

A phytosterol, melting at 134°, was obtained from the unsaponifiable matter.

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Received November 13, 1934.

Parachor and Chemical Constitution. Part III. The Structure of Urea and Thiourea.

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The extensive researches carried out by Werner ("The Chemistry of Urea," Longmans, Green & Co., London, 1923) led him to doubt the validity of the carbamide formula, so universally accepted by chemists to represent the constitution of urea, and to propose a cyclic formula for urea (and thiourea) in the static condition or when present in a neutral solvent.

The object of the present investigations is to find out which of the following two structures agrees with the parachor contribution of the urea and thiourea molecules:

